

DELAMINATION CONTROL IN COMPOSITE BEAMS USING PIEZOELECTRIC ACTUATORS

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SUMMARY

Composite materials have poor tolerance to impact loads. They initially absorb impact energy by creating fracture surfaces, such as matrix cracks and delaminations. In the present work, the possibilities of using of piezoelectric materials to control delamination in composite beams, subjected to low velocity impact are investigated.

Keywords: Composite beam, low-velocity impact, delamination, piezoelectric, cohesive

INTRODUCTION

The need for lighter materials with improved strength and stiffness capabilities has led to the extensive use of fibre reinforced composite laminates in aerospace applications. This is because composite laminates can be designed to have stiffness and strength characteristics that are far superior to any conventional metals or alloys but weigh substantially less [1]. However, a major setback with the use of composite laminates is their poor impact performance. Impact is an inevitable occurrence in aerospace environment. Typical examples would include runway debris impacting aircraft structures during takeoff and landing, bird strikes during flight, tool drops and accidents during component manufacturing and handling [2].

The impact response of laminated composites has been shown to be considerably different to that of isotropic materials [3]. Beyond a damage sustaining limit most isotropic materials dissipate energy via plastic deformation. However, composite laminates have complex failure mechanisms which are normally exhibited in the form of damages such matrix cracks, delaminations and fibre breakages at various locations in the laminate, Figure 1 [4]. These damages are typical for the case of non-penetrating impact such as low velocity impact. In the case of high velocity impact, in addition to the above mentioned damages, a complete perforation of target may also ensue. However, the damages caused by low velocity impact are mostly internal and commonly termed as barely visible impact damage (BVID) [2]. These damages will remain hidden within structural component during its service life and if left unattended pose severe threat to structural integrity and have been a topic of concern for many years. The formation of matrix cracks is quite considerable during an impact but has been shown not to have a significant contribution to the overall reduction of the structural stiffness [5]. However, they result in delamination, which is considered as a

major and most debilitating threat to structural integrity [5]. Consequently, there are various methods that have been used to improve the damage tolerance of composite laminates [6].

Figure 1: Impact induced damages in a $[(0/90)_4]_s$ Carbon/Epoxy laminate [4]

Over the past few years piezoelectric materials have gain entry into a wide range of structural applications [7]. One of the earliest use of piezoelectric materials in structural applications was demonstrated in vibration control of cantilevered beam using polyvinyl fluoride actuator (PVDF) bonded to the surface [8]. When exposed to an electric field the PVDF actuator developed actuation strains which were used to counter the vibration of the beam. Today, a wide range of piezoelectric materials are available and their structural related applications have been extended to include shape control, vibration control, noise and acoustic control and health monitoring [7]. There are several studies that have also suggested that piezoelectric materials hold the potential to detect and suppress damages such as delamination in composite structures [9].

This paper reports the possible use of piezoelectric materials to either reduce or prevent delamination in composite structures due to low velocity impact. For the purpose of this investigation the piezoelectric constitutive model was implemented into Ls-Dyna through its *user defined material* routine. The delamination was modelled using a cohesive based damage model [4].

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT AND DELAMINATION

Delamination due to low velocity impact is primarily caused by high through thickness shear stresses and this has been verified through numerous experimental investigations [3]. From the numerical aspect, there are many approaches towards investigating delamination in composite laminates. Many investigations have relied on the use of stress based failure criteria to model failure in composites [2]. However, these methods are strongly associated with mesh dependency hence making them computationally expensive [4]. In addition, these methods are also affected by numerical noise, which may lead to premature failure indication [4]. Consequently, fracture mechanics was seen as an alternative approach to model delamination. However, the use of fracture mechanics requires an initial crack front in the analysis [2]. The use of cohesive element, which is based on damage mechanics, has been seen as a more realistic

approach to predict failure in composite laminates as it overcomes many of the problems associated with the earlier failure models [2,4].

The cohesive element used to model delamination in the present study is based on a finite thickness solid element, as in a true sense a cohesive element is a representation of the resin layer which indeed has a finite thickness. The element formulation is based on bilinear traction-relative displacement relationship which describes the initiation and growth of delamination, Figure 2. A complete description of the formulation can be found in reference [4].

Figure 2: (a) Bilinear relationship for mode I delamination, (b) Bilinear relationship for mode II delamination

PIEZOELECTRICITY

Piezoelectric materials are basically ferroelectric polycrystals with the ability to couple their mechanical and electrical responses. These are known as the *converse* and *direct* effects. The *converse* effect describes the ability of the material to undergo deformation when subjected to an electric field and the *direct* effect describes the ability of the material to generate electric charges when subjected to stresses or strains [10]. These effects are described in the constitutive form as follows [10]:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\varepsilon\} &= [S]\{\sigma\} + [d]\{E_v\} \\ \{D\} &= [d]^T\{\sigma\} + [\kappa]\{E_v\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where: ε , S , σ , d , E_v , D and κ are the respective strain, elastic constant, stress, piezoelectric strain constant, electric field, electric displacement and dielectric permittivity matrices. Due to its *converse* and *direct* behaviors, a piezoelectric material is applicable both as a sensor and actuator. As an actuator the effectiveness of a piezoelectric material to induce actuation depends on its strain constants. In general, actuators such as piezopolymers have very low strain constants; making them relatively poor actuators compared piezoceramics which generally have higher strain constants. However, piezopolymers are generally flexible and this makes them ideal as sensors.

Though ceramic actuators can induce very high strains, the applications are mostly limited due to their brittleness. The Macro Fibre Composite (MFC) is a new type of actuator with improved flexibility and actuation capabilities [11]. The actuation technology of MFC actuator is based on Inter-Digitated Electrodes (IDE) which allows in-plane actuation rather than out of plane actuation, Figure 3 [11]. Since the strain constants are normally higher in the poling direction, MFC offers improved in-plane actuation, almost twice greater than that of G-1195 piezoceramics.

Figure 3: Configuration and actuation technology of piezoelectric actuators: (a) arrangement for PVDF or PZT actuator, (b) arrangement for MFC actuator

RESEARCH APPROACH

As a preliminary study to the current objective a Matlab based 3-dimensional finite element programme was developed by the authors to investigate the effects of piezoelectric actuation on shape control of composite plates [12]. To study the effect of piezoelectric actuation on the impact response of composite materials, the piezoelectric constitutive equation was introduced into Ls-Dyna through its *user defined material routine*. Equation (1) was modified and expressed in its incremental forms as follows:

$$\{\sigma\}_{\text{new}} = \{\sigma\}_{\text{old}} + [S]^{-1}\{\Delta\varepsilon\} - [S]^{-1}[d]\{\Delta E_v\} \quad (2)$$

where, σ_{new} is the updated stress and σ_{old} is the stress from the previous time step. The symbol Δ indicates that the variables of concern are expressed in their incremental form.

For a composite laminate subjected to low velocity impact, it has been shown that there exists a critical force, P_c , for delamination to initiate and propagate [3]:

$$P_c^2 = \frac{8\pi^2 E (2h)^3 G_{\text{IIC}}}{9(1 - \nu^2)} \quad (3)$$

From Equation (3) it can be seen that the critical force for delamination to initiate depends on the laminate bending stiffness and mode II critical energy release rate. Piezoelectric materials can be used to induce bending in structures and this can be

achieved by appropriately placing them onto the host structure and applying actuation voltages. A simple piezoelectric beam bending model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Piezoelectric beam bending model

Assuming a linear strain distribution, the strain ε_x , across the beam can be written as:

$$\varepsilon_x = zC_x \quad (4)$$

The stresses in the beam and the piezoelectric material can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{sx} &= E_s z C_x \\ \sigma_{ax} &= E_a (z C_x - \varepsilon_a) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where, C_x and E are the slope due to bending and elastic modulus respectively. The subscripts s and a denote the beam and actuator accordingly. ε_a is the induced piezoelectric strain defined as:

$$\varepsilon_a = d_{31} E_v \quad (6)$$

where, d_{31} is the piezoelectric strain constant in the longitudinal direction. Solving Equation (5) for the moment equilibrium gives:

$$C_x = -\frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{(2ht + t^2)}{(3h^2t + 3ht^2 + t^3) + \frac{E_s}{E_a} h^3} \right] d_{31} E_v \quad (7)$$

The above equation shows that the induced bending is proportional to the actuator properties such as thickness, elastic modulus, electric field and piezoelectric constant. In this context the effect of induced piezoelectric moment on the impact response of composite beam are investigated.

NUMERICAL VALIDATION

A numerical test was conducted to validate the accuracy and reliability of implemented *umat material* model. The geometric and physical properties of the experimental setup of a cantilevered PVDF bimorph beam obtained from [13] are shown in Figure 5. For the finite element modelling, the beam was discretized into $100 \times 1 \times 2$ elements along a , b and c respectively. Table 1 shows that the results from the Ls-Dyna *umat* model compare well with the results of other theoretical models. However, due to the assumption of perfect bonding the theoretical results shows higher displacements as compared to the experimental result. All the reference results in Table 1 were obtained from [13].

Figure 5: Experimental set up of PVDF bimorph beam

Table 1: Deflection along the length of the PVDF bimorph beam

Model	Deflection ($\times 10^{-4}$ mm) at				
	20mm	40mm	60mm	80mm	100mm
Experiment [13]	-	-	-	-	3.15
Theory [13]	0.138	0.552	1.24	2.21	3.45
FEM [13]	0.137	0.550	1.24	2.21	3.45
Ls-Dyna (present)	0.138	0.555	1.24	2.21	3.46

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT ON COMPOSITE BEAM

To study the effect of piezoelectric actuation on the impact response of composite materials a composite beam with a stacking sequence of (0/90/0/0/90/0/MFC/MFC) was considered. The material and geometric properties of the composite beam are given in Table 2. The cohesive layers were introduced in between each pair of composite plies. It was assumed that the actuators cover the whole surface of the beam as shown in Figure 6 and do not detach from the composite layer during the impact. A perfect bonding was

assumed between the plies and actuators and between the actuators to ensure no loss of strain transfer from the actuators to the substrate layers. The beam was actuated with 3.5kV prior to impact assuming that the incoming impact was detectable using proximity sensors. A cylindrical steel impactor with a radius of 6.35mm and weight of 0.2kg was considered. The impact energy was set at 1.77J.

Table 2: Material and geometric properties of composite beam

Properties	Carbon/Epoxy [4]	MFC [11,14]
E_{11}, E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	140, 9.5, 9.5	30.3, 15.9, 11.4
G_{12}, G_{23}, G_{13} (GPa)	5.8, 5.8, 5.8	5.5, 2.1, 2.6
$\nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}$	0.3, 0.3, 0.3	0.31, 0.29, 0.33
ρ (kg/m ³)	1540	4750
$\sigma_{o,I}, \sigma_{o,II}, \sigma_{o,III}$ (MPa)	57, 100, 100	-
$G_{IC}, G_{IIC}, G_{IIIC}$ (N/mm)	0.281, 0.900, 0.900	-
d_{11}, d_{12}, d_{13} (pm/V)	-	460, -210, -210
length, width, thickness (mm) – per ply	75, 5, 0.25	75, 5, 0.3

Figure 6: Finite element model of Carbon/Epoxy beam with bonded MFC actuators

Figure 7 shows the contact force-time history curves of the impact with and without piezoelectric actuation. It can be seen that under the piezoelectric actuation, the contact force curve exhibits a symmetric behavior indicating there is no loss in the structural stiffness signifying no damage has occurred. Figure 9 confirms no damage has taken place as the impact energy is preserved under the actuation state. However, the contact

force without actuation is shown to drop, indicating loss of stiffness due to damage, Figures 7 and 8. This is confirmed by the drop in the impact energy level, Figure 9. Figure 8 shows that the drop in the contact force is sudden once damage has begun. It was also observed that the actuation increased the stiffness of the beam; this was evident from the shift in the impact energy curve and reduced peak displacement, Figures 9 and 10 respectively. Figure 8 shows that under the actuation state the threshold force for damage to initiate has been shifted due to the increase in the laminate stiffness.

Figure 7: Contact force-time plot for 1.77J impact

Figure 8: Closer view of the contact force-time plot for 1.77J impact

Some oscillations were observed in the impact energy-time plot once damage has initiated, Figure 9. This was due to the sudden and disproportionate damage growth in the laminate which eventually led to abrupt stiffness loss in the structure.

Figure 9: Impactor kinetic energy-time plot for 1.77J impact

Figure 10: Beam centre displacement-time plot for 1.77J impact

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is evident from the described analysis piezoelectric material can be used to control delamination in composite laminates by increasing its stiffness through proper actuation. In the present approach the issue of the applied voltages was not considered. However, actuators have limits on the maximum and minimum applicable voltages. In light of this, a design optimization study would be required to find the optimal location and voltage distribution on actuators to ensure a more realistic implementation. Nevertheless, the present study has demonstrated the potential capabilities of piezoelectric actuators to be used as an active damage control tool.

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